

Media Access And Usage In The Development Of A Community In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The effectiveness and efficiency of any development programme, is dependent on extent the media of communication considered to convey development messages. It is dependent also to the level of community acceptance and participation of the development and sustainability of the programme. This phenomenon has birthed several research efforts in the area of development studies, particularly on the use of strategic and appropriate communication messages and channels to achieve sustainable development. This study therefore is a comparative examination of the different ways in which both traditional modes of communication, contemporary mass media and the new media, which is also refers as (Strategic Communication) could be used to achieve sustainable development in a rural community. The theory underpinning this study is the diffusion of innovation theory, which beliefs that an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among members of a social circle. A survey design was used, where a 20-item questionnaire was administered to 200 respondents in Nri Community, Anambra State in order to determine how the different communication modes could be used to achieve sustainable development. The data generated were analyzed using frequency distribution and simple percentage. Study findings indicate that there is need that appropriate integration of contemporary media, the new media and traditional communication system, is considered as the best communication strategy that will be appropriate and sustain development goals in rural areas. This is because various modes of communication have their unique characteristics and therefore serve different purposes, while some are more persuasive in nature, others are faster in creating awareness, and are more interactive and democratic.

Keywords: Media, Accessibility, Usage, Development, Rural Community, Development Messages.

INTRODUCTION

Communication which entails the act of sharing information and messages from one person to another and one place to another, has become an important feature in sustainable development. Indeed, "communication for development" according to Fraser, Burch, Knightly, Osborne and Wilson (2002) has become a significant and recognized field among many development change agents and policy-makers. The opening for this discourse is borne out of there cognition that in sustainable development there are multiple key players, all generating and sharing information. It therefore becomes important, build bridges, link different opinions and create a common "language" among different key players. Communication in the form of interpersonal, group, mass media or machine- mediated media and the new media is often needed to support and facilitate development in social, cultural, economic and technical areas. Since the fields of development are many and varied, communication facilitating functions also tend to be many, though generally quite similar.

However, the challenge of selecting and using appropriate channels and communication strategies to gain development initiatives have been a major areas of concern for development scholars in developed and developing societies. In Nigeria for example, several negative attempts at rural development in the past have unfortunately contributed to many unsustainable development projects.

As Nwuneli(1985) cited in Okunna (2002) clearly reveals:

In most developing countries, development projects have continued to fail because development agents have persistently selected and used inappropriate channels in disseminating information to the grassroots, making the development message not to be effectively channeled to the people. (p.298).

Supporting Nwuneli, Omenugha and Afolayan (2010) collaborated in their agreements that laudable as these projects may seem, they were marred with myriads of problems. Amongst them was non-involvement of beneficiary community members in the project conception, planning and implementation, wrong choice of media outfit and language usage. The lesson that could be drawn from the problems identified is the fact that rural development needs community participation from the planning stage, down to the execution of the development projects which would be communicated to them through the appropriate media available and preferred bythem. Ezeah (2005) as cited in Omenugha and Afolayan (2010) posited that, development provides a favorable context for consideration through the use of the appropriate communication strategies.

Considering the above, it becomes clearer that development programmes and projects can only be realized if knowledge and technology are shared effectively, and development beneficiaries are motivated and committed to achieve success. Unless target individuals are the driving force of their own development, no amount of investment or provision of technology and inputs will achieve any sustainable improvement in their living standards. Appropriate communication strategy is therefore key to this task in many ways. For example, it enables planners, when identifying and formulating development programmes to reach out to the people in order to take into account their needs, aspirations, attitudes and traditional knowledge. Only with appropriate communication will project beneficiaries become the principal actors to make development programmes successful and achievable. Communication succeeds when it is part of the key strategy to set development priorities and carry out planning, implementation and evaluation of programmes, and also when it is employed to improve training at all levels (FAO, 2000).The question now is which particular mode of communication is most available, accessible, preferable for implementing development programmes in rural community?

Statement Of Research Problem

Many unachievable development projects scattered all over the developing world, especially the under developed countries like Nigeria, have negative stories to the concept of development as interpreted by policy makers in the developing world. This has nothing to do with lack of knowledge, but largely dependent on corruption and poor planning that these so-called development projects do not see the light of day. If development is understood to mean simply, a gradual growth or advancement through progressive changes, then there must be a channel for attaining to those changes. This is where the communication process or strategy comes into play, that is, the strategic and well-directed programme of delivering development messages to targeted people who will initially assess and highlight their development needs before working with the benefactors to execute them.

Consequently, there has been the search for the appropriate channel (usually available and preferable to the targeted community) which will assist to convey development messages effectively, thereby using communication to achieve development goals and objectives. This is the main point of this work.

Objectives Of The Study

This study seeks to find how strategic communication could be used to achieve sustainable development programmes in rural communities.

Specifically, the objectives of the study are:

1. To find out the media of communication that is more accessible, effective and preferred in creating awareness of development programmes in rural community in Anambra state.
2. To ascertain the appropriate persuasive media that can influence people's attitude and help indecision- making in the select community.

3. Find out the most appropriate media of communication for planning and implementing development projects in the select community.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

CONCEPTUALIZING DEVELOPMENT

Development is a concept that is usually applied by scholars in various disciplines. Rodney (1972, p.9) is of the opinion that development is a many sided process. He opined further that development is a process of planning and engaging in activities that are aimed at effecting positive changes, which should positively affect the society by empowering the citizens towards progressive, healthy, economical and educational upliftment. The essence of development the overall improvement on the general wellbeing of individuals. The positive changes and effects of development is the major concern of various scholars.

Okunna (2002) clearly states that:

Although “development” can mean different things to different people, it has become generally acceptable that there are unique features which should characterize any process of development. For instance, development should bring change, this change should be targeted for the better, the change should be for the benefit of the majority of the people and the process should involve participation (p.294).

Based on the above, development simply refers to the act of introducing new ideas, ways, or improvement to change the society into a new form or status. This transformation or modification in relative form is seen as a change from a less developed and ancient form to a more modernist or contemporary status with the use of a model of another society whose state of development is viewed as a desirable goal (Wilson, 2005, p.123). He further explained that the concept of development, which is placed on the introduction of innovations, involves positive change or transformation in all aspects of life of the people.

The Concept of Sustainable Development

Sustainable development has been defined in several ways, but the most frequently quoted definition is from Our Common Future, "Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the contemporary without compromising the ability of the next generations to meet their own needs and aspirations." In other words, sustainable development refers to a mode of human development in which resource use targeted to meeting human needs, with the aim of ensuring the sustainability of natural systems and the environment, so that these needs can be met not only in the present, but also for generations to come (United Nations, 1987; Smith & Rees, 1998).

The Concept of Development In Nigeria

It is imperative at this juncture to identify the specific forms of innovations and development projects that can be channeled through the use of traditional, conventional and the new media. According to Wilson (2005, p.128), some of the development issues that confront Nigeria and other developing countries like Nigeria include:

1. Self-reliance: independence in agricultural activities and other needs;
2. Education and elimination of illiteracy among the people;
3. Economic recovery, development and the eradication of poverty;
4. Democratization and mass participation (mobilization) in the economic, political and social life of the citizens with particular emphasis on popular participation in self-development planning and actualization; etc.

However, the target and aim is towards developing underdeveloped countries gave birth to the establishment of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The Millennium Development Goals came to the fore from the Millennium Declaration which was agreed upon by heads of states in the year2000.

THE CONCEPT OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION

During the past two decades, the purposeful application of media and communication support has increased to an increasingly important role in many forms of development. Much of it has been lied under the larger movement normally referred to as Development Communication(DevCom).The term development communication was originally coined by Nora Quebral of the University of Philippines in the 1962 (Manyozo, 2006). The concept of development communication is characterized by conceptual flexibility and diversity of communication techniques and ways used to address the problem. Quebral, defines development communication as the “art and science of human communication linked to a society’s planned transformation and change from a state of penury to one of dynamic socio-economic growth that contributes to greater equity and the larger unfolding of individual potentials” (Manyozo, 2006).

Communications experts from various fields have, however, tried to define the term to reflect their own understanding of the concept. Broadly defined by the U.S. AID, development communication refers to "the application of existing communication technologies and media types to the problems of development" (AID, 1984, p.i). The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) more precisely summarized development communication as "the systematic utilization of appropriate communication channels and techniques to increase participation of beneficiaries in development and to inform, motivate, and train rural people, mainly at the grassroots level" (Coldevin, 1987, p. 4).

In the later definition, development communication refers to the systematically practice and the application of the processes, strategies and principles of communication to effect positive social change which will support sustainable change in development operations.

Paterson (2011) believes that development communication is an organized efforts to apply communications processes and the media to effect social and economic improvements. Development communication, which is often used side by side with the term development journalism, is at once an easy concept to define but also seen as an extremely contentious subject. Its simplicity comes from the fact that everybody knows that communication in the journalistic sense refers to the dissemination of information to mass audiences and that when that is mixed to the word development, then we are clearly referring to communication that seeks to support and promote the process of development.

Edeani (1993, p.126) explains that development communication “denotes the employment of all facets of communication, and not only the mass media, in the promotion of national development efforts.”Rogers (1995) in his own opinion believes that development communication is an educational process that aims at developing social consciousness, personal responsibility towards one’s counterpart, community and country. Development communication implies respect for the human person, his intelligence and his right to self-determination.

It found its coherent articulation in Everett M. Rogers’s “diffusion of innovations” theory. The scholars who helped this ‘modernisation’ approach to development posit development communication as an life wire of change from the ‘traditional’ to the ‘modern’ society and generally assumed that a nation became truly modern and developed when it develops at the point where it closely resembled Western industrial nations in terms of political and economic activities and institutional attitudes towards technology and innovation, and social and psychic mobility. Thus, for Banda, the role of the mass media would be not only to create awareness, but also an interest in the innovations espoused bybene factors or change agents. It was also glaring that this mechanism was characterized to a large extent by the two-step flow model of media influence, with the notion of “opinion leaders” playing an important role in birthing modernizing practices among their fellow citizens (Banda, 2007). Today, it has been recognized that psycho-social life skills are important. These skills consists of decision-making, problem solving, critical thinking and creative thinking. Others are communication skills, interpersonal relationship skills, empathy, as well as self awareness, and coping with stress and emotions. In addition, educational systems, cultural, religious, socio-political, socio-economic and physical environmental factors will either help or hinder the adoption of new behavioural changes. These elements of the environment must be carefully considered when designing programmes (Eyiah, 2004).

The issue of values cut across all of the aforementioned factors. Values are expressed by perceptions, attitudes and beliefs and these must be carefully surveyed and understood for programmes to be effective. If we do not take people's value systems into consideration, the programme will go south (Freire, 1972). Part of the process of development lies in finding appropriate means and modes of communicating its ideals and plans to the most ideal and significant segment of the population. Indeed, many scholars have argued that most development plans do not see the light of the day, partly on account of the failure of communication or the absence of it. Wilson (1988) as cited in Wilson (2005) aptly argued that, no rural development programme which does not involve the target people of its benefits and employ appropriate media can succeed if at the stage of conceptualization and planning before execution, it distances itself from the people and their preferred media of communication channels, only to seek their support at the implementation stage. A communication for rural development policy would target to promote diffusion of information about non-agricultural micro-enterprise development, small business planning, nutrition, healthcare and generally serve to provide useful information (Manyozo, 2006).

MEDIA OF COMMUNICATION FOR DEVELOPMENT

It is fashionable and novel to maintain that the problem of appropriate choice of media and channels for rural development must be studied in its social context and that there is no generally valid blueprint available for a particular media for channeling development messages to the target audience. Traditional media as well as modern media of communication are both valuable, depending on the situation, purpose and their availability.

THE CONCEPT OF TRADITIONAL MEDIA

Many scholars have proffered definitions of traditional communication. A common concept in these definitions is the idea of being embedded in the culture and collectively all the ways of doing things of a community or people (Akpabio, 2003, p. 2). Traditional communication systems or grassroot communication systems encapsulate the story that is ingrained in the culture of the community. It brings to bear the channels that are embedded within the traditional beliefs of a people and contributing greatly to their history and culture (Jussawalla & Hughes, 1984, p. 225).

For generations, rural populations living in isolated villages without access to modern facilities of communication have relied on the face to face communications and traditional forms of communication as a means of sharing knowledge and information and providing entertainment. Indigenous or Traditional Communication Systems refer to all organized processes of production and exchange of information managed by rural dwellers. Some of the traditional channels of communication like traditional theatre, masks and puppets performances, tales, proverbs, riddles and jokes, masquerading, local drum and gong languages, and songs, should be employed as a cultural and indigenous response to different community needs for information, education, social protest as well as entertainment. These systems are often employed to solve the contradiction between the need for change of a rural community and the need to preserve its cultural heritage. There is a high rate of illiteracy and poverty added to the inadequacy of the mass media to reach almost 700 million people who reside in rural communities. To them, the mass media proved to be glamorous, impersonal and unbelievable to compare to the familiar performance of traditional artist whom the villagers could not only visualize, hear but even feel emotionally. In other words, all communication processes based on media which are not birthed and managed by the rural community themselves, like radio, video, newspapers, television and the new media, are not taken as traditional and are considered foreign to the rural community. They often ignore the communication process of a particular ethnic lining or rural community: how the group produces and gets information, what media and tools are gained, and what role do the "traditional communicators" such as community leaders, contact farmers and extension workers play?

Traditional media has a remarkable impact on rural communities because of their acceptable idioms, functional significance and entertainment concepts. Traditional media can overcome the difficulty of language, speech, words and other problems of communication like, interest, understanding, interpretation, attitude and perception. These traditional media will not only help in development

activities, but will also assist in preserving and transmitting culture, tradition and values to the future generation.

Communication is a product of culture, and culture is determinant on the code, structure, meaning and context of the communication that takes place. The participation of local folk artists, storytellers and performers in the production and use of traditional media encapsulate respect for traditional values, symbols and realities and, at the same time, ensures that such media productions appeal to target audiences. Citizens' use of local media and communication channels also increases the credibility of media programmes and vis a vis their effectiveness and impact on the knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of rural populace.

The preservation of traditional forms of communication and social change are not mutually excluded. Traditional communication methods can be important channels for facilitating learning, attitudinal change, participation and dialogue for development purposes. Indigenous media have been successfully accepted by change agents to promote rural development. They have been used, for instance, to influence attitudes towards family size, female genital cuttings, teenage pregnancies, unsettling lifestyles and HIV/AIDS. They have also been used in environmental protection and literacy programmes, as well as in teaching about maternal and child nutrition and in introducing new agricultural practices. For illiterate rural people in particular, occasions for information sharing has consisted significantly in local festivities, family gatherings, traditional and religious associations as well as interaction with itinerant merchants and encounters at market square or water streams. This mechanism affords the younger generations of the opportunity to communicate their needs and raise their issues in the presence of the whole community through an existing and culturally accepted channel of communication.

CONVENTIONAL MEDIA

Mass media is an artificial channel used in transmitting information or messages to a large heterogeneous and scattered audience at the same time. The mass media in this context include, newspaper, radio and television. Mass communication at the service of development —or “development communication” — should seek to elicit a human and to a large extent a social response in the people whom it seeks to serve. The role of mass communication is to assist, not to overtake or substitute for his thought. It serves him by providing the facts on which to base a sound judgment, and the inspiration to carry out his assignment.

According to Okunna (1999), the mass media serves important functions in the society by accepting and fulfilling certain tasks by the society. These tasks are mainly to be met by setting high professional standards of informativeness, truth, accuracy, objectivity and balance. The media in general should be pluralistic and reflect the diversity of their society by giving access to various points, opinions and rights to reply. The mass media plays a crucial role in community development. It is therefore incumbent upon our ethnic media (community newspaper and local FM radio stations) to keep our communities connected to the past by communicating the stories and traditions we hold dearly. At the same time, such media connects our communities to the present and to the next generation by sharing images and news of our people around the world and forming the foundation and values for posterity to continue.

Beijing Declaration (1996) identified the mass media as having great potential to promote the advancement and development of rural communities. In particular, it states that "television especially has the greatest impact on young people and as such, has the ability to shape values, attitudes and perceptions of people in both positive and negative perspectives." Indeed, television is a prestigious, powerful and empowering tool that can create awareness, generate discussion and increase knowledge about every aspect of life.

Eyiah (2004) further explained that radio, whether national, regional or local in reach has also contributed to the main stay for many multi-media campaigns, the most powerful of strategies in disseminating information and building motivation especially at the grassroots. Radio remains the most effective, and yet the cheapest mass medium for reaching large number of people even in remotest areas. It is easily affordable, portable and accessible. Radio has the characteristic of closing the gap of distance, illiteracy and language diversity better than any other medium of communication” (FAO, 1996, p. 9).

Radio can also promote dialogue and debate on the major issues of rural development, as well as providing a platform for the expression of rural people's interests, opinions and aspirations. Radio is a tool of communication that can be used to develop community cohesion and solidarity. Community involvement is fundamental for the successful use of radio with rural populations. Radio programmes are most effective when produced with audience participation, in local languages and with consideration for cultural integration. Successful features include, but not limited to live public shows, quizzes, village debates and the most recent, phone-in programmes. Community radios treat issues concerning the everyday life of their audience and also promote local development.

THE CONCEPT OF NEW MEDIA

Since the early 1970s, sustainable development has shifted from the realm of activist political players to professional implementers to the popular vocabulary. Earlier media tools such as television, radio, newspapers, journals and Web sites were employed by sustainable development advocates to attempt to “sell” the concept. However, these were largely a one-way conversations from experts to their key players and audiences. Capturing people’s attention was a teething challenge.

However, research has shown that Social Networking Services, such as (Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, WhatsApp, Blogs, MySpace, Bebo, BBM, LinkedIn, Hangouts, Instagram etc) are now aiding the sharing of sustainable development concepts more rapidly through peer learning. People pay more attention to what their trusted sources and friends have to convince them with. Information sharing is moving speedily between and across social networking sites through not only technology features (e.g. Twitter: “tweets” can be automatically uploaded and displayed as Facebook status updates), but also through key netizens active on multiple platforms. Gladwell (2000) notes that similar to epidemics, a handful of unique people play an important role in starting idea epidemics. They translate the message of innovators into something understandable. They alter it in a way that extraneous details are shared and others are exaggerated so that the message itself comes to acquire deeper understanding. To begin an idea epidemic, the following roles and skill sets must be present in a social network:

- **Mavens**—These individuals are known as idea specialists. They are human databanks who are obsessive about details and goes on to share them with others;
- **Connectors**—Connectors are people specialists. They are equipped with the knowledge of people from every possible sub-culture and niche. They have an extraordinary knack for making friends and acquaintances out of every individual, either from a farmer in a village to vice-presidents of international banks; and
- **Salespeople** – These individuals have the skills to persuade people when they are unconvinced of what they are hearing. They are masters of the art of emotional expression and have the powers to draw people into their own conversational rhythms on a completely subconscious level.

Therefore, with improved SNS tools, mavens, connectors and salespeople are all becoming more equipped in efficiently and effectively initiating idea epidemics. On mainstream SNSs, the notion of sustainable development action has been some what “dumbed down” to a lowest common denominator. While this is somewhat inevitable in order to ensure broad-scale support for a complex idea, it is still somewhat troubling. Through SNSs, people have become used to feeling good about themselves for sending virtual plants to each other (at which point a corporate ad sponsor pays to save the rainforest), indicating they are “fans” of organizations or causes, and creating lists of the green actions they already take in their daily lives. These are very low-cost actions for people to take.

Despite the advantages that abound in the use of the social media to create awareness about innovations, there are certain shortcomings noted which can thwart the effectiveness of the use of such media in rural development. Millions of people in rural areas have no access to new media due to some factors like incompetence in technology, poverty and illiteracy level as well as no access to electricity. With 35 per cent of the population not lettered and with the media's reach largely restricted to urban areas - information, education and entertainment through the new media may not reach a large majority of the rural people.

While social media may build awareness of issues, there is no research indicating whether people gain a deeper commitment to sustainable development through these activities or whether these lead to taking more actions.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND STRATEGIC COMMUNICATION

The analysis of the traditional, conventional and the new media indicates that no single medium of communication is completely better than the other. Circumstances and requirements of the development project determine the form of communication that will be enough. Audience survey concerning what media the people can have access to and which enjoy credibility, and what is actually available or could be realistically established, greatly characterize the choice of media. However, it should be remembered that a message arriving in a slightly different form and through different channels has the most impact in assisting individuals towards behavioural change. Hence, multi-media approaches are usually the most effective (Hamelin, 1990). Berelson (1960) as cited in Okunna (1999) believes that, "Some kinds of communication on some kinds of issues, brought to the attention of some kinds of individuals, under some kind of conditions, experience some kinds of effects".

Strategic communication is a powerful tool that can enhance the chances of success of development projects. It includes all the activities required for identifying and assessing critical issues, designing and implementing appropriate strategies, and monitoring and evaluating results. It is an active and empowering solicitation of the stakeholders' perspective, ensuring that mechanisms are rightfully placed for a two-way flow of information. A Strategic Communication framework serves multiple important roles in the development process and takes into consideration psychological, socio-political, cultural, and economic dynamics within and across key players groups directly or indirectly involved in the development process. The Strategic Communication intervention is a combination of a variety of information, education, mobilization, behaviour change, and capacity building activities that assist facilitate horizontal and vertical relationship building, top-down and bottom-up political move, accountability, process management, social and behavioural change through knowledge and learning.

Strategic communication strives for behavioural change not just information dissemination, education, or awareness-creation. All development requires some kind of behavioural change on the part of key players. In order to effect behavioural change, it is necessary to understand the reason people behave the way they do and understand the barriers to change or adopting new practices. It is not enough to raise awareness of the "benefits", it is important to understand peoples' barriers or the "costs" they perceive such a change would entail. Well- conceived, professionally implemented communication programmes that are hinged directly to reform efforts or development project objectives that bring the knowledge of local political, social and cultural realities to bear in the design of development programmes can make the difference between a project's success and failure.

Strategic Communication Process

As earlier stated, communication is a process that entails a number of approaches, tools and products, which can be identified and implemented according to circumstances. This process according to Mefalopulos and Grenna (2004) can be structured in three basic broad areas:

1. Communication Research (Problem Analysis)

In the first stage, all important inputs for the project communication strategy should be identified. The role of communication is mainly analytical. Dialogue therefore becomes key to identify relevant key players, probe their perceptions, investigate their needs and aspirations and problems, knowledge sharing and identification of the situation that the change agents intend to thwart. Communication here supports other analytical work by enhancing trust, facilitating the sharing of information and reaching a common understanding of the situation. At this stage, the final output of communication is the definition of the communication objectives and not the objectives of the development projects. A baseline survey is carried out and communication is employed to identify and set indicators and means for evaluation, to later be used to ascertain the communication programme implementation and assess the impact of the communication strategy.

2. Communication Design Concept and Implementation (Problem Solving)

At this stage, communication applications have a role which is applicable to the usual conception of communication. Nevertheless, it can be used in several ways according to the needs. The following are some of the most frequently used communication approaches, which are not mutually exclusive: dialogue, social marketing, advocacy or lobbying, dissemination of information, institutional strengthening, capacity building that entails training/education and community mobilization. These approaches can be used individually or combined to achieve the intended aims.

3. Communication Monitoring Concept and Evaluation (Solution Assessment)

Having set the indicators and criteria for evaluation in the first lap of the communication process that is, Communication Research, these are used to monitor, assess and evaluate the communication strategy in the third phase.

THEORETICALFRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on the 'Diffusion of Innovation Theory' which posits that an innovation is communicated through certain channels of communication over time among the citizens of a social system. Rogers (1995) posits that there are four main elements that influence the spread of a new idea: the innovation, communication channels, time, and a social system.

Modernization is here birthed as a process of diffusion whereby people move from indigenous ways of life to a more complex, more technically developed and more rapid way of life. This approach is therefore concerned on the process of diffusion and adoption of innovations in a more systematic and organized way. He distinguishes between five phases in the diffusion theory: awareness, interest, evaluation, trial, and adoption. The role of communication channels is concentrated in the first phase of the process, whereas personal sources are most essential at the evaluation in the adoption process (Rogers, 1962, p. 99). In the second phase of his work Roggers and Shoemaker (1973), argue that there are only four crucial steps left in the process of diffusion and adoption: the knowledge of the innovation itself (information), the communication of the innovation (persuasion), the decision to adopt or reject the innovation (adoption or rejection), and the confirmation of the innovation by the people (Servaes, 1999).

RESEARCHMETHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey method. The survey method was considered appropriate for this study because of the benefits abound in surveys that can be a great benefit to the social researcher. Significant among these benefits is the ability to bring together equivalent information from a large number of individuals swiftly and economically, by throwing the same questions to each and recording the answers in standard format. Survey gives the researcher the opportunity to measure characteristics, behaviour and opinion of a population by studying a small sample from that group and then generalization is employed to the population under study based on their expression opinions on promoting sustainable development through strategic communication..

A 20-item questionnaire was administered to 200 respondents who were randomly selected from 6 villages in Nri community in Anaocha L.G.A of Anambra State. This study was limited to Nri because the community is noted as one of the communities in Anambra state with a good number of development projects that are not sustained. This can be exemplified by un- sustained development projects like; non functional Akamkpisi water borehole, Nri Community Bank among other unsustainable development projects.

There are six villages in Nri. The six villages were purposively selected, because they experience the same problem of abandoned rural development projects in the community.

Table One: Sampling Frame

The information in table one above indicates the number of respondents selected randomly from the chosen villages according to the population of each village. 40 respondents representing 20% were from Akamkpisi Village, 30 respondents representing 15% were from Diodo, 35 respondents representing 18%

were from Ekwenanyika, 25 respondents representing 11% were from Obeagu, 35 respondents representing 18% were from Uruoji, 35 respondents representing 18% were from Agbadani village in Nri.

Table 1: Sampling Frame

Villages	No. of Respondents	Percentage(%)
Akamkpisi	40	20%
Diodo	30	15%
Ekwenanyika	35	18%
Obeagu	25	11%
Uruoji	35	18%
Agbadani	35	18%
Total	200	100%

DISCUSSIONOFFINDINGS

Research Question 1: *Which of these media is more available, effective and preferred in creating awareness of development programmes in rural community in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Respondents ‘Major Source of Information

Media	Percentage
Radio	28%
Television	9%
Newspapers	6%
Friends and relations	13%
Community leaders	11%
Social gathering	8%
Traditional newsmen	12%
Markets	5%
New Media	9%
Total	100% (N=200)

The data in Table 2 indicates that 28% of the respondents get their first hand information from the radio; 9% receives information from the television; 6% of the respondents receive from newspapers; 13% gets theirs from friends and relations; 11% of the respondents get information from the community leaders; 8% receives information from social gathering; 12% get news from traditional newsmen, while 5% and 9% of the same respondents get their first hand information from markets and new media respectively. This result suggests that majority of respondents receives their firsthand information from the mass media and the indigenous media.

Research Question 2: *Which media is more appropriate and can influence people’s attitude and persuasiveness in decision making in the select community?*

Table 3: Reasons for Respondents ‘Media Preference

Media	Always Available and Accessible	Mostly Affordable	Very Informative
Radio	22%	23%	23%
Television	9%	4%	9%
Newspapers	5%	3%	7%
Friends and Relations	14%	16%	15%
Community Leaders	16%	17%	14%
Social Gathering	13%	10%	9%
Traditional Newsmen	11%	18%	14%
Markets	7%	5%	6%
New Media	5%	7%	6%
Total	100% (N=200)	100% (N=200)	100% (N=200)

The data in Table 3 indicates that 22% of the entire respondents prefer listening to radio because it is always available, accessible and effective , 16%of the respondents prefer getting information from community leaders because of their availability and accessibility , 14% of the respondents prefer information from family and relations as their major source of information because they are always available and accessibility, 13% of the respondents prefer information from social gathering due to the same aforementioned reason, 9% of the respondents depend on television because they are available and accessible, 11% prefer traditional newsmen, 5% prefer the new media, while 7% and 5% of the same respondents depend on markets and newspapers respectively as their major source of information because they are always available and accessible and effective.

The data also show that 23% of the entire respondents prefer radio because of its mostly affordable, 17% of the respondents prefer community leaders because they are also mostly affordable, 16% of the respondents prefer family and friends because they are mostly affordable, meanwhile 18% of respondents prefer traditional newsmen, due to the same reason, 10% of the respondents prefer gathering, 5% of the respondents prefer market places, 7% of the respondents prefer the New Media, while 4% and 3% of the same respondents prefer television and newspapers respectively as their major source of information due its affordability.

The data also reveal that 22% of the respondents prefer radio because it is very informative, 15% of the respondents prefer friends and relations, 14% of the respondents prefer community leaders, while 12% of the respondents prefer town criers because they are highly informative. The data also show that 9% of the same respondents prefer social forum because it is highly informative, another 9% of the respondents prefer television, 6% of the respondents prefer the New Media, while 7% and 6% of the same respondents prefer newspapers and market places respectively as their source of information because they take them to be highly informative.

In order to answer research question 1, the information in tables 2 and 3 show that people prefer and expose themselves regularly and frequently to mass media and indigenous media, more than the new media. This is because they see them as more , accessible, reliable and effective in creating awareness of development messages to the rural populace. This therefore goes to agree with the inference in the literature that mass communication is an effective tool in creating information and for innovation awareness (Lazarfield, 1975).

Schramm (1964, p.43) collaborated with Lazarfield’s in his, view on the role of mass media, by asserting that the spread of knowledge through mass media “provides a climate and opportunity for national

development. It makes the expert knowledge available where it is needed, and provides forum for discussion, leadership and decision-making process”. Therefore, the findings of Lazarfield (1975), Goonasekera (1987), Duylin (1979) and Onyishi (2000) reaffirm that mass media especially radio and the traditional media like, traditional newsmen, are more available, accessible, preferred and most effective in creating awareness of development messages in the rural community.

Research Question 2: *Which media is more appropriate and can influence people’s attitude and persuasiveness in decision making in the select community?*

Table 4: Respondents’ Most Appropriate\Persuasive/Influencing Media.

Media	Percentage
Radio	13%
Television	8%
Newspapers	6%
Friends and Relations	22%
Community Leaders	16%
Social Gathering	10%
Traditional Newsmen	7%
Markets	11%
New Media	8%
Total	100% (N=200)

The data in table 4 indicates that 22% of the entire respondents believes that friends and relations are their most persuasive media of communication, 16% believes that community leaders persuade most, 8% of the respondents believe information from the New Media influences them most, 11% believes that market places are where they get persuasive information mostly, while 7% of the respondents believe that traditional newsmen persuade them most. The table also reveals that 13% of the respondents believe that radio is the most influential media, 8% believe television is the most persuasive media, while 6% of the same respondents believe newspaper is the most persuasive media of communication for planning and implementing development projects. The results therefore suggest that majority of the respondents believe that interpersonal or face to face modes of communication are more persuasive than mass communication in disseminating and accepting of development messages. The findings indicate that conventional media (television, newspaper and new media), despite their effectiveness in creating awareness was discovered to be ineffective in persuasion, attitude change and decision-making, as indigenous modes of communication are topping the chat, apart fro radio.

This affirms the observation of Moemeka (1994, p.150) as cited in Akpabio (2003) that interpersonal channels which are integral part of traditional communication are important in overcoming selective exposure and perception as well as ensuring feedback and its ability to meet local needs and bring about positive change in attitude.

Research Question 3: Which of these media is most appropriate channel of communication for planning and implementing development projects in the select community?

Table 5: The media that Aids in Planning and Decision-Making

Media	Percentage
Radio	9%
Television	7%
Newspapers	2%
Friends and Relations	20%
Community Leaders	20%
Social Gathering	10%
Traditional Newsmen	18%
Markets	8%
New Media	6%
Total	100% (N=200)

The data in Table 5 indicate that information from radio aids 9% of the respondents in planning and decision-making, messages from Television is most appropriate as 7% of the respondents help in planning and decision-making, messages from newspapers aid 2% of the respondents in decision-making, information from friends and relations help 20% of the respondents planning and in decision-making, messages from community leaders is most appropriate as 20% of the respondents, help in decision-making, while messages from social gathering aid 10% of the respondents in planning and in decision-making. The table also shows that information from traditional newsmen, aid 18% of the respondents both in planning and in decision-making, information from the New Media aid 6% of the respondents in decision-making, while messages from market places aid 8% of the entire respondents in decision-making. This table therefore indicates that majority of the respondents returned the responses that interpersonal modes of communication plays significant roles in their planning and decision-making than the mass communication.

This finding also affirmed the literature when Lazarfield (1975) in conjunction with Columbia University, studied the role of mass media on the way audiences make up their minds on deciding on issues. To their surprise, they found the effect to be rather insignificant. They gained the impression that people appear to be much influenced in their decisions by face-to-face contact or through inter personal relationship with other people - members of their family, friends, neighbours, social groups, community leaders and their colleagues. However, Lazarfield and his crew discovered that interpersonal communication is somewhat more likely to reach and affect people who are yet undecided than mass media.

Duylin (1979) in his book "Media and Mass Communication in Nigeria" accepted that in decision-making, social relation is bound to play an important role. Another unique finding was that the majority of respondents believe that messages from traditional modes of communication because of its ownership and control, having the view, that the messages from the mass media are highly biased as a result of government control over the mass media and its content.

CONCLUSION

From the data gathered and the analysis, there is no agreed singular appropriate media for communicating development information. This is because all forms of communication have unique roles they play in achieving sustainable development. Strategic Communication intervention is found to be one of the best means through which access to and application of knowledge and information are facilitated. Strategic Communication intervention provides development agents with the support they need, as well as serves as an enhancing tool for the achievement of development objectives. It also helps to facilitate a common

understanding among participants of the development initiative, thus creating an avenue for concerted action. Thus, the use of different communication channels, that is, integrating traditional and local media, contemporary mass media and the new media, in a coordinated and mutually reinforcing way gives the appropriate results in achieving sustainable development in rural communities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. This study recommends the adoption of strategic communication to all operators change agents and managers of developmental projects in rural communities in Anambra State, since all forms of communication have unique roles they play in achieving sustainable development.
2. Government agents and operators of rural development projects should ascertain the existing indigenous forms of communication methods. existing in their areas of operation with a view to integrating the relevant traditional communication modes into their planning and execution. This drive or initiative will help convince people for participation hence the sustainability of the development projects in the areas

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